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Determinants of Olive Baboons' Food Choice in Kainji Lake National Park Nigeria

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Abstract

*Olive baboons (*Papio anubis*) are ecologically flexible and generalist feeders yet selective in choice of diet. Insufficient information on the plants consumed by olive baboons and their dietary preference hinders appropriate and deliberate conservation measures. This study therefore identified the plant species, dominant plant part consumed by olive baboons in Kainji Lake National Park (KLNP), Nigeria and unravelled the basis for their predominant diet choice. Direct observation method was used to record food plant species and plant parts consumed by olive baboons in KLNP for a period of 24 months. Twenty two plant species belonging to 16 families were identified. Plant parts consumed by olive baboons included fruits (92.0%), tuber (4%) and roots (4%). Fruit was the dominant plant part consumed by olive baboons. All year round availability, avoidance of conspecific competition and predation, energy cost, nutritional consideration, immune system stability and reduced risk of parasitic infection were the determining factors of olive baboon fruit propensity. Olive baboons' frugivorous tendency has far reaching ecological implications with attendant effect on seed dispersal, seed treatment, seed predation, food provisioning, food competition and food scarcity among other sympatric animals. There is need for research into these ecological interactions and other implications of olive baboons' frugivorous propensity.*

Keywords: food, olive baboon, frugivory, Kainji Lake National Park

INTRODUCTION

Primates consume a wide variety of foodstuffs which primarily includes fruits, leaves and invertebrates but also seed, gums, lichens, bark, roots and in some cases other vertebrates such as mammals, aves and reptiles as well as invertebrates like crabs and insects. Assessing dietary properties is important to a number of areas relevant to primatologists, including life history, ecology and behaviour. Knowledge of the dietary requirements of primates can equally help conservation managers better protect their habitats, and provide insight for captive care managers (Rothman *et al.*, 2013).

All free ranging animals make choices regarding which food to eat, with these choices influencing their nutritional state and ultimately their health and fitness (Altmann 1998; Beehner *et al.*, 2006). Investigating the dietary selection in primates has provided a unique understanding of their foraging strategies and provided means to explore determinant of primate abundance (Whiten *et al.*, 1991; Oates *et al.*, 1990). Understanding the determinants of primate abundance is becoming increasingly important as ecologists are tasked to assist conservation biologists to construct informed management plans for endangered species. This has become critical because most primates live in tropical forests which are increasingly being impacted by human modification (National Research Council, 1992).

Collectively, 125,140 km² of forest are lost annually across the geographic distribution of primates, resulting in the annual loss of 32 million primates (Chapman and Peres, 2001), the reason being that these forests serve as

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source of food and shelter for primates. In fact, global analysis on the status of world mammals indicated that primates are the order most threatened by extinction. These populations are also being seriously harmed by forest degradation, particularly logging and fire, and hunting. For example, if important tree species could be left standing in selective logging operations, population declines following logging might be lower and/or the speed of recovery might be more rapid for those species negatively affected by logging (Chapman *et al.*, 2003).

The starting point however is to identify the important tree species that provide food resources and shelter for these primates. Olive baboon (*Papio anubis*), being the focal animal of the study is one of the primate species widely distributed in Kainji Lake National Park (KLNP), Nigeria. Olive baboons face the risk of malnutrition when there is decline in the quality and quantity of available forages. This may lead to reduced productivity or consequently extermination from the park. Insufficient information on the food plants consumed by olive baboons and their dietary preference in KLNP hinders appropriate and deliberate conservation measures to be adopted. There is need for up to date information on the feeding ecology of olive baboons in KLNP in order to consolidate on strategies for the management and conservation of Olive baboons in the park. Haage *et al.* (2017) attested to the fact that basis for dietary preference and specialization are not fully known, which therefore calls for investigation. Findings from this study will be valuable for the management of captive primate populations and other forms of ex situ conservation. Studies conducted on food choice of free ranging animals are vital for re-introduction of wild animals. Findings from such researches also help in habitat improvement efforts (Haage *et al.* 2017). Not only that, studying wild animals' feeding ecology and preferences are vital for understanding their nutritional requirement, which is essential for breeding and survival (Altmann 1998). Investigating the food types preferred by wild animals could lend insight into the food species that may have bearing on feeding competition and habitat degradation. It will also help to identify plant species and habitat that should be prioritized for conservation programmes (Provenza, 1995a).

This underscores the relevance and importance of this study. This study however identified the plant species, dominant plant parts consumed by olive baboons and also attempted to unravel the basis for their choice of fruit diet.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

This research was conducted in Kainji Lake National Park, Nigeria. The Park was established in 1979 by the merger of two former non-contiguous game reserves (Borgu and Zugurma) into one entity. It covers a total area of 5,340.82 km². The two sectors (Borgu and Zugurma) of KLNP lie approximately between latitudes 9⁰ 40'N and 10⁰ 30'N and longitudes 3⁰ 30'E and 5⁰ 50'E respectively (Aremu *et al.*, 2000). KLNP is situated in the boundary between the North and South of Guinea Savanna. Riparian Forests also occur on the banks of larger water courses. Generally, the vegetation is described as been Northern Guinea Savanna types which as formations of mosaic of plant communities contrasting in structure. The topography of the park is gently undulating with general decrease in elevation from West to East. Some areas are hilly with the highest elevation of about 300-350m above sea level. The park is drained by a network of rivers and streams, all of which empty into the rivers Oli, Timo and Doro while the drainage in Zugurma sector consists of rivers Manyara and RuwaZorugi. The park has a yearly circle of dry and wet season based on Northern Savanna climate. The wet season begins from April to October while the dry season is from November to early April with a short harmattan period between mid-December and February. The annual rainfall ranges from 975mm to 1220mm. KLNP has about 59 plant families. The dominant tree species include; *Burkea africana*, *Detarium microcarpum*, *Azalia africana*, *Isobertina tomentosa*, *Acacia spp.* etc. There are over 66 species of large mammals represented by about 13 artiodactyls, 10 carnivores and 5 primate species. The area is also rich in bats, birds and insects. In addition, there are also 62 species of fish belonging to 20 families and 28 species of reptiles and amphibians. Examples of the animal species in the park include Roan antelope (*Hippotragus equinus*), Olive baboon (*Papio anubis*), Patas monkey (*Erythrocebus patas*) Buffalo (*Syncerus caffer*), Kobs (*Kobus kob*), Hippopotamus (*Hippopotamus amphibus*) etc. (Ayeni, 2007).

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Method of Data Collection

Direct observation method was adopted in eliciting information on the feeding activities of olive baboons in the study area while they foraged. This is achieved through the following procedures:

i. Trailing System

This involved following behind tracing (through the foot prints and fresh fecal droppings) of the animals especially in the evening from drinking sites (water holes such as rivers and streams) to their sleeping sites. Often times, olive baboons retire from water points in the evening to their sleeping sites. However it is worthy of note to state that considerable and appropriate distances were kept away from the animals depending on the visibility and vegetation cover. The minimum distance kept was 5m. This was to avoid the study animals from being agitated and to ensure that the observers were not attacked by the study animals.

ii. Auditory Clues

Olive baboons` feeding sites were identified by trailing their vocalization such as long, alarm calls, warning barks and other forms of vocal communications they made right from the sleeping sites before departure for foraging in the morning. Their vocalizations were traced from 05:00hrs. The study was conducted for a period of 24 months covering wet and dry seasons.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages and pie charts were used to present results of plant species consumed proportion of plant parts consumed.

RESULTS

Olive baboons obtained their food from a total of 22 plant species belonging to 16 families during the entire study period (Table 1). Fruits formed the dominant (92%) plant part consumed while roots (4%) and tubers (4%) constituted the remaining portion (Figure 1).

From the outcome of the study, olive baboon`s diet in Kainji Lake National Park (KLNP) consisted predominantly of fruits from various plant species. The ingestion of fruit is called frugivory while animals that feed on fruits are referred to as being frugivorous. Frugivorous tendency of olive baboons in KLNP cut across both dry and wet seasons. In other words their frugivorous tendency was not season specific. Olive baboons are often times referred to as being ecologically flexible and generalist feeders, yet they are selective or specialized feeders. For instance, Altmann and Altmann (1970) described baboons as generalist omnivores with their diet comprising numerous types of plants, invertebrates and small vertebrate animals while Clark (1982) opined that the diet of omnivores; a group in which olive baboons belong, is rarely restricted to one type of food. Primates generally eat different types of food ranging from plant parts such as seeds, fruits, leaves, and gum to animals such as insects, larvae, reptiles and small mammals.

Despite being generalist feeders, olive baboons can yet be selective in the choice of their diet. Whiten *et al.* (1987) characterized baboons as eclectic but highly selective feeders. Certain wild animals sometimes show preference for a particular food type even when they are acclaimed to be a generalist feeders (Haage *et al.*, 2017) Olive baboons were highly selective in their choice of diet in the study area giving preference for fruits. This scenario was also observed among olive baboons in Budongo Forest Reserve, Uganda (Okecha and Newton-Fisher, 2006). However, a predominantly fruit diet of olive baboons in the study areas did not translate into the actual vegetation composition of their habitat. The feeding strategy of generalist feeders may not be an indication of the actual ecology because dietary specialization may play out (Araujo *et al.*, 2011). For instance European mink *Mustela lutreola* regarded as a generalist feeder was found to exhibit dietary specialization (Haage *et al.*, 2017).

Based on the result of this study and other similar researches conducted among various olive baboon populations, there appears to be a nexus between olive baboons and fruits. Olive baboons in KLNP consumed more fruits than any other plant part. Their preference for fruit has also been observed by Akosim *et al.* (2010) in Hong Hills, Adamawa state, Nigeria, where out of the identified sixteen plant species foraged by Olive baboon, the fruit of fourteen of them were consumed by the baboons.

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In Sukerbosrand Nature Reserve, South Africa, over 60% of diet in late wet season contained fruits and seeds (Segal, 2008). Kunz and Linsenmair (2008) also attested to baboon's frugivorous tendency as they reported that baboons in Comoé National Park, Ivory Coast were largely frugivorous spending about 50% of their feeding time on fruits and seeds. They equally reported that Olive baboons at Shai Hills in Ghana spent a high amount of their feeding time on fruits and seeds.

In addition, fruits constituted a large portion of the diet of baboons in Bylde Canyon Nature Reserve, South Africa, accounting for 62% of the total forage effort while utilization of and reliance on other food types such as pods and roots only increased in dry season to compensate for the decline in fruit availability (Marias, 2005). This implies that their consumption of other food types increased in dry season during the period of fruit shortage but there was no fruit shortage in KLNP during the dry season but rather an increase. This could explain why olive baboons in the study area were consistent with feeding on fruits in both dry and wet seasons. Further support for the view that baboons have preference for fruits over other food types is the outcome of the study on the diet of olive baboon in Budongo Forest Reserve, Uganda. They spent the largest proportion (47%) of feeding time on fruits and seeds (Okecha and Newton-Fisher, 2006).

Determining factors of olive baboons fruit choice in KLNP

With all the aforementioned case studies, a question then comes to mind; what are the drivers or probable factors responsible for olive baboon's preference for fruit in KLNP. The following factors suggest their preference for fruits.

1. All Year Round Availability

Going by the outcome of the study, a variety of fruits were available as food for the focal animal all year round. There was no period that baboons experienced fruit scarcity, unlike availability of young foliage that is highly seasonal especially in savanna habitat where young leaf flushes are often seasonal events. In savanna habitats, trees shed their leaves in dry season and growth of new leaves is often synchronized with wet season.

This was not the case with fruits that baboons could access at any season or period of the year in the study area because plants produce fruits at different times of the year. Consequently fruits of some kind were available year round unlike the seasonal availability of leaves.

Furthermore, animals choose food items based on temporal and spatial food availability among other several other factors (Jordano, 2000). Previous studies have linked feeding strategies of free ranging animals to food availability (Elliot Smith *et al.*, 2015 ; Rosenblatt *et al.*, 2015).

Diet choice in animals is influenced by seasonal trends in environment variables which in turn influence plant and animal resource levels and availability within different habitat types (Alberts *et al.*, 2005). This seasonality favoured an all year round availability of fruits for baboon consumption in KLNP.

2. Avoidance of Conspecific Competition and Predation

For the purpose of reducing conspecific feeding competition and vulnerability to predation, olive baboons in KLNP resorted into feeding often on fruits that could quickly be harvested in contrast to other food types like subterranean foods such as roots, tubers, rhizomes and bulbs which imposes more time on prospective consumers. Spending long hours extracting underground plant parts exposes primates and other prey animals to predation. Predators often trail their preys to feeding and drinking points. Baboons are not exempted from the risk of predation. For instance chacma baboon (*Papio hamadryas*) at Moremi Game Reserve in Botswana had elevated mortality predominantly due to predation. Staying long on a particular food item exposes baboons to risk of predation especially in savanna grassland (and other exposed micro habitat) with clear visibility. In a bid to reduce vulnerability to predation, baboons have developed adaptive and survival behaviours by spending minimal time in harvesting food items. This is evident in possession of a morphological feature called cheek pouch. Cheek pouch is a specialized sac on the inside of baboon cheek (Rowe, 1996) used for short term food shortage (Altmann, 1998) and allows baboon to gather as much food as possible (Hayes *et al.*, 1992) within the shortest period of time. Cheek pouches are used commonly when feeding on fruits (Lambert, 2005). For avoidance of predation, it follows therefore that baboons will prefer to forage on food that, as much quantity as possible, can easily and quickly be harvested within the shortest period of time. By implication, baboons

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favoured harvesting of fruits over subterranean foods such as roots and tubers in KLNP. Svanbäck and Bolnick (2007) and Coleman and Wilson (1998) correlated dietary specialization with intraspecific competition and risk evasiveness through avoidance of predators.

3. Energy Cost

Free ranging, unprovisioned primates and other wild animals are confronted with different options when foraging such as when or where to forage on and for how long to forage (Kamil *et al.*, 1987, Menzel and Wyers, 1987). This implies foraging behaviour is associated with cost and benefits (Stephens and Krebs, 1986). The benefit being the energy gained from the food while the cost is energy expended in searching and processing of the food such as digging and uprooting. Different food types require differing degrees of manipulation and energy cost: plant parts such as tubers and roots require more degree of manipulation and energy cost than fruits (Clymer, 2006). Even when other food types like plant parts available, bearing in mind the effort and energy cost required to access them, especially when other less energy demanding food types like fruits are available, as it was the case in KLNP, underground plant part may not be predominant in olive baboon choice of diet. This can in a way explain why olive baboons in KLNP frequently sought for more fruits than any other plant parts.

4. Nutritional Consideration

Food choice of Olive baboon in KLNP just like other wild animals was driven by a complex set of criteria, prominent among which was the nutritional content of the potential food item. Olive baboons' fruit use in the study area could have been influenced by the various fruits' nutritional content. Olive baboons' selectivity or choice of diet is premised on the basis of meeting energy and nutritional needs as well as the digestibility of the food item. Optimal Foraging Theory predicts that an animal forages in a manner that optimizes energy gain (Perry and Pianka, 1997). Wild animals' preference for a particular food type rises when their nutritional requirements are met but declines when the food is inadequate in nutrients and contains toxins beyond what the animal can tolerate (Provenza, 1995a). Primates, just like other wildlife species exhibit preference for foods that cater for their nutritional needs (Provenza, 1995b). In other words, nutritional requirements informs an animal's food preference or feeding strategy (Provenza, 1996). Furthermore, such feeding strategy would minimize as much as possible, the consumption of toxins (Freeland and Janzen, 1974).

Nutritive value of fruits coupled with moisture content, fibre and quantity of secondary compounds is capable of affecting baboon fruit choice (Glander, 1982). The variety of fruit species in the diet of olive baboons in the study area implies that the fruits provided nourishment. Ripe fruit contains high sugar and carbohydrate levels (Kunz and Linemair, 2007) while seed provide a good source of protein and fatty acids (Heller *et al.*, 2002).

Fruits, especially those of animal dispersed species (edible fruits) are composed primarily of a succulent flesh that provides a rich source of simple sugars and water. In comparison, the sugar content in fruit is more than double of what is contained in flowers (Richard, 1985). Furthermore, fruits are easy to digest and their protein content is not hindered by secondary plant compounds to the extent seen in leaves (Ganzhorn *et al.*, 2009).

5. Immune System Stability

Apart from the more apparent explanations earlier given for baboon fruit choice in KLNP, there could be other intrinsic factors that favoured fruit selection in baboon diet choice. One of such is a link between fruits consumption and immune stability of the focal animals. The non-seasonality or year round availability of fruits in KLNP eliminates or better still, minimizes the possibility of dry season-induced dietary stress. Seasonality of resources caused by dry season is capable of inducing dietary stress as resources availability declines, depressing the immune system (Nelson, 2004; Chapman *et al.*, 2006). So rather than the Olive baboons in KLNP have depressed immune system due to food shortage, their immune system will at least be stable, if not enhanced by year round availability of fruits. Animals that depend on seasonal food would be more prone to starvation and diseases.

6. Reduced Risk of Parasitic Infection

Frugivorous primates including baboons eat less volume of food when compared to leaf eating primates. This implies that leaf-eating primates have tendency to ingest more parasites than the fruit-eating (Gogarten *et al.*, 2012) exposing them to different parasitic infections. To corroborate this view, comparative studies showed that

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extent of folivory is positively correlated with diversity of helminth species across primate species (Nunn *et al.*, 2003; Vitone *et al.*, 2004). In essence, the more olive baboons include fruits in their diet, the less the risk of parasitic infection.

CONCLUSION

Olive baboons in KLN fed on a variety of plant species. However their diet comprised predominantly of fruits irrespective of season. Olive baboons' frugivorous tendency has far reaching ecological implications. Their fruit diet will have effect on seed dispersal, seed treatment, seed predation, food provisioning, food competition and food scarcity among other sympatric animals that have fruits constituting a portion of their diet. This calls for research into these ecological interactions and other implications of olive baboons' frugivorous propensity. Efforts should also be geared towards habitat improvements and conservation of identified food plant species in the park in order to ensure the perpetuity of the animals in the park. There should also be further studies on the spatial variation of olive baboons' food plant species vis-à-vis their distribution and habitat utilization.

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LEGEND

Table 1: Plants Species Consumed By Olive Baboons in Kainji Lake National Park

Figure 1: Proportion of Plant Parts Consumed by Olive baboons in Kainji Lake National Park

ABBREVIATIONS

KLNP: Kainji Lake National Park

Table 1

S/N	Plant Species	Family	Parts Consumed
1.	<i>Dioscorea rotundata</i>	Dioscoreaceae	Tuber
2.	<i>Cochlospermum tinctorium</i>	Cochlospermaceae	Root
3.	<i>Swartzia madagascariensis</i>	Fabaceae	Fruit
4.	<i>Isoblerina doka</i>	Fabaceae	Fruit
5.	<i>Kigelia africana</i>	Bignoniaceae	Fruit
6.	<i>Ficus sycamoros</i>	Moraceae	Fruit
7.	<i>Grewia molle</i>	Malvaceae	Fruit
8.	<i>Piliostigma thonningii</i>	Fabaceae	Fruit
9.	<i>Vitelaria paradoxa</i>	Sapotaceae	Fruit
10.	<i>Icacina trichantha</i>	Icacinaceae	Fruit
11.	<i>Vitex chrysoarpa</i>	Lamiaceae	Fruit
12.	<i>Afzelia africana</i>	Fabaceae	Fruit
13.	<i>Xamenia americana</i>	Olacaceae	Fruit
14.	<i>Detarium microcarpum</i>	Caesalpinaceae	Fruit
15.	<i>Parkia biglobosa</i>	Fabaceae	Fruit
16.	<i>Gardenia sotoemesis</i>	Rubiaceae	Fruit
17.	<i>Tamarindus indica</i>	Fabaceae	Fruit
18.	<i>Strychnus spinosa</i>	Strychnaceae	Fruit
19.	<i>Spondias mombin</i>	Anacardiaceae	Fruit
20.	<i>Nauclea latifolia</i>	Rubiaceae	Fruit
21.	<i>Oncoba spinosa</i>	Salicaceae	Fruit
22.	<i>Adansonia digitata</i>	Bombacaceae	Fruit

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Figure 1